

Table 2. Effect of *S. rostrata* (SR) on rice grain yield, straw yield, and nutrient uptake of rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)		
	1987	1988	Pooled mean	1987	1988	Pooled mean	1987	1988	Pooled mean
SR only	3.6	5.5	4.6	5.8	7.5	6.7	35.60	55.86	45.78
SR + 25 kg N/ha	3.9	5.9	4.9	6.1	8.0	7.0	35.34	58.79	47.06
SR + 50 kg N/ha	4.2	6.3	5.3	6.1	8.3	7.2	39.57	63.17	51.37
SR + 75 kg N/ha	4.5	6.7	5.6	6.4	8.4	7.4	43.49	67.49	55.49
SR+ 100 kg N/ha	4.9	6.9	5.9	6.0	8.8	7.4	43.62	71.94	57.78
Control (100 kg N/ha)	3.8	5.2	4.5	6.0	8.1	7.1	17.91	35.70	26.80
LSD at (0.05)	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.3	1.33	2.19	1.26

Rice response to N application with different irrigation schedules

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To determine a suitable time for N and irrigation water application to maximize yield, we conducted studies at two sites in the Ganges-Kobadak (G.K.) irrigation project area.

BR11 was used in T. aman season (Jul-Dec) plantings in 1988 and 1989, and BRL in aus (Mar-Jul) 1988. Soil was silty loam with pH 7.5-8.0, 0.80-0.85% organic matter, and CEC 18-20 meq/100 g soil. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

NPK were applied at 80-26-33 kg/ha as urea (45% N), TSP (20% P), and

KCl (50% K). All the TSP and KCl were applied basal and urea was topdressed in three equal splits at 10-d intervals from transplanting. The treatments are in the table. Approximately 5-7 cm water was applied during each irrigation.

Soil incorporation of fertilizer N (T3) produced the highest rice yield in both locations. Compared with the control (T1), rice yield increased by 11-38% for T3 and by 5-29% for T2.

The low yield in T1 may be attributed to denitrification and washing out of N with deep percolating water and surface runoff. T3 may have minimized such loss of N.

This study suggests that to maximize yields in rotational gravity irrigation systems like the G.K. project, fertilizer N should be applied at the end of irrigation and should be incorporated. ■

Incorporation of *S. rostrata* alone gave as much grain yield as did control. Increasing applied N with *S. rostrata* further increased grain yield. However straw yields in control and with 50 kg N/ha at *S. rostrata* incorporation were similar (Table 2).

S. rostrata gave significantly higher N for plant uptake than did control. ■

Yield response of modern rice varieties to fertilizer N applied at different times of irrigation at 2 sites in the G.K. project area.

Treatment no. ^a	Mean yield ^b (t/ha)	
	Swastipur	Shaillkupa
<i>T. aman 1988</i>		
1	4.3 c	3.7 c
2	5.0 b	4.5 b
3	5.4 a	4.8 a
<i>Aus 1989</i>		
1	3.4 b	3.9 b
2	4.3 a	4.4 b
3	4.6 a	5.5 a
<i>T. aman 1989</i>		
1	4.2	4.9 b
2	4.5	5.8 a
3	4.7	6.3 a

^a 1 = fertilizer N applied 1 d before irrigation; 2 = fertilizer N applied after completion of irrigation, 3 = fertilizer N applied after completion of irrigation, followed by incorporation the following day. ^b In a column, values followed by a common letter do not vary significantly (LSD).

Integrated pest management — diseases

Effect of inoculum source on sheath blight (ShB) development

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IR72 (highly susceptible), IR64 (susceptible), and IR26957-86-2 (moderately resistant) were inoculated at booting stage with four ShB inoculum sources in a screenhouse experiment during 1989 dry season. The sources were 1) mycelial blocks of *Rhizoctonia solani* from a 5-d-

old culture on potato dextrose agar (PDA), 2) sclerotia from a 10-d-old culture on PDA, 3) 1-wk-old culture from rice grain-hull mixture, and 4) freshly infected rice stems from a field of IR72.

Rice grain-hull inoculum and infected stems were placed directly at the base of each hill. Mycelial discs and sclerotia were placed in tissue paper at the base of the rice plant.

Highest relative lesion height was used to determine disease development from 5 plants in each pot up to 6 times at 5-d intervals.

Disease development differed significantly (see table). In control pots where

Area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) based on highest relative lesion height (%) of 3 rice cultivars inoculated with different inoculum sources in the screenhouse, 1989.^a

Treatment	AUDPC		
	IR64	IR72	IR26957-86-2
Mycelia	922.94 ay	1121.06 ax	703.25 az
Rice grain-hull	971.19 ax	1068.63 ax	680.00 ay
Sclerotia	974.69 ax	1046.38 ax	780.50 ay
Infected rice stem	422.63 bx	378.81 bx	420.81 bx
Control	0.00cx	0.00cx	0.00cx
CV (%)			
Cultivar -	15.49		
Treatment -	19.66		

^a Mean of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter in a column (a, b, c) or in a row (x, y, z) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.